

Liechtenstein

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Liechtenstein, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the higher education system of Liechtenstein does not distinguish between the different types of higher educational institutions (Universities, Universities of applied sciences, Universities of teacher training) as is common in the other German-speaking countries. But the law does include a discretionary provision which allows higher education institutions to give themselves a specific profile by developing strengths in teaching and research. The Higher Education Law specifies the following orientations:

- the provision of research- and theory-oriented content;
- the provision of content that is oriented towards practical applications and/or based on research and theory.

In addition, the framework law sets out the possible legal forms of institutions of higher education. These are either institutions or foundations based on public law or legal entities in private law. However, regardless of their legal form, all institutions of higher education - including those based in Liechtenstein which offer distance learning - are subjects to approval by the government and are subject to the same legal rules.

Currently, the higher education sector in Liechtenstein comprises two recognised institutions:

- University of Liechtenstein providing bachelor, master, doctorate and further education programmes
- Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein (UFL) providing doctorate and further education programmes

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics of the two Universities in Liechtenstein. The University of Liechtenstein (Universität Liechtenstein) is a private government-

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/liechtenstein/types-higher-education-institutions>

dependent institution, while the Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein (Private Universität im Fürstentum Liechtenstein) is a private institution. Both Universities award PhDs.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2019

Category		N	Private	Private government- dependent	PhD awarding
University	Universität	2	1	1	2
Total		2	1	1	2

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

The University of Liechtenstein (Universität Liechtenstein) was established in 1961 as Abendtechnikum Vaduz and got later formally recognized as University of applied sciences (Fachhochschule), under the name Liechtensteinische Ingenieurschule (LIS). In 2005, the University of applied sciences was transformed from a Fachhochschule to the Hochschule Liechtenstein, and finally in 2011 it became the University of Liechtenstein.

The Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein (Private Universität im Fürstentum Liechtenstein) was first established in 2000, under the name University of Humanistic Sciences in the Principality of Liechtenstein. In 2007 it received governmental approval and in 2008 the name was changed to Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein.

Students

In 2020, a total of 343 Bachelor students and 325 Master students were enrolled at the University of Liechtenstein (no Bachelor or Master students at the Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein). However, the Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein accounted for 164 of the 204 PhD students in Liechtenstein.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

In 2020, the two Institutions in Liechtenstein employed a total of 73 academic personnel (FTE), 60 research and teaching assistants and 68 support and administrative personnel. However, the University of Liechtenstein employed more than 90% of all personnel across all categories.

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT². Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Liechtenstein data show a steep hierarchy, with only 17% of academic personnel at the senior level. A reasonable gender balance has been achieved for intermediate personnel, but only one out of twenty senior-level academic personnel are female (see **Error! Reference source not found.1**).

Figure 1. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by **Error! Reference source not found.2**, Liechtenstein's higher education is characterized by an extraordinary high level of internationality with 95% of foreign academic personnel (up from 90% in 2011).

² OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 2. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011 and 2020

Financial resources

The University of Liechtenstein had a total of 73 full time equivalents of academic personnel in 2020 with total current revenues of about 16.3 Mio Euros PPPs€ in the same year.

Figure 3. Composition of resources of the University of Liechtenstein, 2020

Looking at the composition of revenues, the University of Liechtenstein receives with a share of about 15% a substantial proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds while student fees contribute another 10% of total revenues. Personnel and financial data for the Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein is missing.

Changing roles over time

The number of students enrolled at the University of Liechtenstein (no Bachelor or Master students at the Private University in the Principality of Liechtenstein) decreased from 854 in 2011 to 668 in 2020. However, since 2014 the total number of students has remained mostly stable.

Figure 4. Students enrolled at the University of Liechtenstein (2011-2020)

Note: Only includes ISCED 6-7

As shown by Figure 5, academic personnel employed at the two Universities in Liechtenstein slightly increased from 64 (FTE) in 2011 to 73 (FTE) in 2020.

Figure 5. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

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